

Reusing data from a completed clinical trial to inform guidelines

“The results of this network meta-analysis have already directly informed the update of UK guidelines.”

- Dr. Sarah Nevitt

Researcher(s) or Team: Dr. Sarah Nevitt, University of Liverpool

Dataset(s) used:

<https://vivli.org/antiepileptic-drug-monotherapy-for-epilepsy-an-updated-cochrane-review-and-individual-participant-data-network-meta-analysis/>

Related publication(s): Nevitt SJ, Sudell M, Cividini S, Marson AG, Tudur Smith C. Antiepileptic drug monotherapy for epilepsy: a network meta-analysis of individual participant data. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews 2022, Issue 4. Art. No.: CD011412. DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD011412.pub4.

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Background:

Dr. Sarah Nevitt and a team of researchers examined the effectiveness of various antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) for people experiencing seizures due to epilepsy. Epilepsy, a common neurological disorder, results from abnormal electrical discharges in the brain, causing recurrent seizures. Typically, around 60% to 70% of individuals with epilepsy achieve longer-term remission, often shortly after beginning treatment with antiepileptic drugs.

For this study, Dr. Nevitt and her fellow researchers sought to compare the time to treatment failure, remission, and first seizure of 12 antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) currently used as monotherapy in children and adults with focal onset seizures or generalized tonic-clonic seizures.

The screenshot shows the NICE website interface. At the top, there's a search bar and navigation links for 'Guidance', 'Standards and indicators', 'Life sciences', 'British National Formulary (BNF)', 'British National Formulary for Children (BNFC)', 'Clinical Knowledge Summaries (CKS)', and 'About'. Below the navigation, the breadcrumb trail reads: 'Home > NICE Guidance > Conditions and diseases > Neurological conditions > Epilepsy'. The main heading is 'Epilepsies in children, young people and adults', with subtext 'NICE guideline | NG217 | Published: 27 April 2022 | Last updated: 30 January 2025'. There are tabs for 'Guidance', 'Tools and resources', 'Information for the public', 'Evidence', and 'History'. A 'Download guidance (PDF)' button is visible. The 'Overview' section contains a table of contents with three items: '1 Diagnosis and assessment of epilepsy', '2 Information and support', and '3 Referral to tertiary specialist services'. A 'Related quality standards' box links to 'Epilepsies in children, young people and adults'. The text below the table states: 'This guideline covers diagnosing and managing epilepsy in children, young people and adults in primary and secondary care, and referral to tertiary services. It aims to improve diagnosis and treatment for different seizure types and epilepsy syndromes, and reduce the risks for people with epilepsy. Last reviewed: 30 January 2025'.

The clinical practice guideline for epilepsies in children, young people and adults produced by the UK's National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) has been updated to reflect findings from Dr. Nevitt's research.

Process:

Dr. Nevitt and her team sought to compare the performance of 12 different AEDs in terms of treatment failure, remission, and occurrence of first seizures among both children and adults with focal onset or generalized tonic-clonic seizures. They analyzed data from an extensive collection of clinical trials encompassing more than 22,000 participants, incorporating individual patient data from various studies using a network meta-analysis (IPD-NMA).

The analysis revealed some key insights. Older drugs like phenobarbitone and phenytoin demonstrated better seizure control for both focal and generalized seizures but had poorer long-term retention rates compared to newer medications such as lamotrigine and levetiracetam. Sodium valproate emerged as the top choice for achieving control and remission of generalized tonic-clonic seizures, although it might not be suitable for everyone, especially people of childbearing age, due to associated risks.

Table 2: Summary of included studies

Study	Population	Interventions	Comparator	Outcomes
Nevitt 2022	Number of studies = 89	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Carbamazepine• Eslicarbazepine acetate	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Each Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Time to treatment withdrawal (treatment failure)
Systematic review and IPD NMA	Number of participants = 22,040	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Gabapentin• Lacosamide• Lamotrigine• Levetiracetam• Oxcarbazepine• Phenobarbitone• Phenytoin• Sodium valproate• Topiramate• Zonisamide		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Time to 12-month remission• Time to 6-month remission• Time to first seizure• Incidence of adverse events

IPD: individual patient data; NMA: network meta-analysis

Summary of key information from the network meta-analysis, including the population, interventions, comparators, and outcomes investigated.

Findings:

IPD were available for at least one outcome specified for this IPD-NMA for 67% of eligible participants, and for 43% of eligible trials. This IPD-NMA provides high to moderate certainty evidence that for people with generalised tonic-clonic seizures, sodium valproate has the best profile compared to other treatments, but lamotrigine and levetiracetam would be the most suitable alternative first-line treatments.

These findings were published as a network meta-analysis in the Cochrane Library. Results from this network meta-analysis have also directly informed the update of UK clinical practice guidelines for treatment of epilepsy, making immediate impact. Guidelines ensure that treatment decisions are consistently based on the best available evidence, and UK guidelines inform those of many other countries worldwide. This research has also been referenced in guidelines for Canada, as well as more than [30 other citations](#).

Graphic from the network meta-analysis published in the Cochrane Library, showing a network plot of pairwise comparisons in all included studies.